

CODEN [USA]: IAJ PBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**ANALYSIS OF SERUM POTASSIUM LEVELS AND
MORTALITY IN ACUTE MYOCARDIAL INFARCTION IN
PAKISTAN**Tooba Ali¹, Qurat ul ain Ali¹, Ahmed Ammar Ali¹¹Sheikh Zayed Hospital Rahim Yar Khan.**Article Received:** August 2019**Accepted:** September 2019**Published:** October 2019**Abstract:**

Hypo- and hyperkalemia have been shown to increase cardiovascular and total mortality in patients with acute myocardial infarction (AMI). Hypokalemia refers to a serum potassium concentration (SPC) of <3.5 mEq/l, occurs frequently in hospitalized patients and is associated with ventricular arrhythmias as well as an overall poor prognosis after cardiovascular events. It is concluded that reduction in sodium level was assessed only in patients with AMI as compared to healthy persons. Estimation of serum electrolyte is of utmost importance for diagnosis and prognosis of AMI.

Corresponding author:**Tooba Ali,**

Sheikh Zayed Hospital Rahim Yar Khan.

QR code

Please cite this article in press Tooba Ali et al., Analysis of Serum Potassium Levels and Mortality in Acute Myocardial Infarction in Pakistan., Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2019; 06(10).

INTRODUCTION:

Hypo- and hyperkalemia have been shown to increase cardiovascular and total mortality in patients with acute myocardial infarction (AMI). Hypokalemia refers to a serum potassium concentration (SPC) of <3.5 mEq/l, occurs frequently in hospitalized patients and is associated with ventricular arrhythmias as well as an overall poor prognosis after cardiovascular events [1]. Hyperkalemia is defined as a SPC of >5.0 mEq/l and can have a variety of adverse consequences, such as cardiac arrhythmias, in patients hospitalized after a cardiovascular event. Extracellular (serum) potassium concentration is normally maintained within the approximate reference range of 3.5-5.2 mmol/L; this is important for normal cardiac function. Both reduced serum potassium (hypokalemia) and increased serum potassium (hyperkalemia) can, if sufficiently severe, be associated with potentially lethal cardiac arrhythmia [2].

Some recommend a higher target of 4.5-5.5 mmol/L. The study, which was conceived to test the validity of this expert advice, involved retrieval of the medical records of 38,689 patients admitted with acute myocardial infarction (AMI) to 67 US hospitals for the period 2000-2008 [3]. Each of these patients was assigned to one of seven groups, depending on their mean serum potassium concentration for the duration of hospital stay [4].

Potassium homeostasis is critical to prevent adverse events in patients with cardiovascular disease. Several studies have demonstrated a relationship between low serum potassium levels, usually less than 3.5 mEq/L, and the risk of ventricular arrhythmias in patients with acute myocardial infarction (AMI) [5].

A recent study sought to determine the impact of plasma potassium concentration for patient survival following myocardial infarction. Current guidelines emphasize the importance of avoiding hypokalemia, advising that patients diagnosed with myocardial

infarction should be given potassium supplements, if necessary, to maintain serum potassium in the range of 4.0-5.0 mmol/L [6].

Objectives of the study:

The basic aim of the study is to analyse the serum potassium levels and mortality in acute myocardial infarction in Pakistan.

METHODOLOGY OF THE STUDY:

This cross sectional study was conducted in Sheikh Zayed Hospital Rahim Yar Khan during January 2019 to June 2019. The data was collected from 100 male and female patients with myocardial infarction. We determine the impact of plasma potassium concentration for patient survival following myocardial infarction. Current guidelines emphasize the importance of avoiding hypokalemia, advising that patients diagnosed with myocardial infarction should be given potassium supplements, if necessary, to maintain serum potassium in the range of 4.0-5.0 mmol/L. Serum potassium was measured in the emergency department and repeatedly thereafter throughout hospitalization, and was used in the analysis, along with a large array of clinical and laboratory variables.

Statistical analysis:

The data was collected and analysed using SPSS version 19.0. All the values were expressed in mean and standard deviation.

RESULTS:

The data was collected from 100 patients of MI. Mean age of male patients was found to be 64.12 ± 12.34 and female patients was 46.21 ± 10.24 . There was statistically significant decrease in serum sodium and potassium levels in study group among both the ages compared to normal healthy control group. Serum sodium, potassium, chloride, calcium levels were significantly lower in the AMI patients and magnesium levels were slightly raised among cases than controls.

Table 01: Analysis of comparison of electrolytes

Serum (mmol/L)	case	control	p-value
Sodium	82.641 \pm 6.412	94.612 \pm 5.241	0.001
Potassium	4.234 \pm 1.156	4.562 \pm 1.214	0.728
Magnesium	6.624 \pm 2.562	2.431 \pm 1.124	0.001
Chloride	72.421 \pm 6.561	78.432 \pm 6.112	0.134
Calcium	3.431 \pm 0.456	4.428 \pm 1.141	0.005

DISCUSSION:

Most likely there is also an increase in circulatory catecholamines in patients with an unconfirmed myocardial infarction. Patients with anterior infarction and those with larger infarcts tended to have more hypokalemic episodes than those with inferior and those with smaller infarcts. Such findings raise the possibility that the association between infarct size and the occurrence of severe ventricular arrhythmias, which has previously been could, to some extent, depend on the more frequent development of hypokalemia in patients with large infarcts [7]. Our results fit with the hypothesis that a higher sympathetic tone increases the risk for development of hypokalemia. On the other hand, a higher initial heart rate did not significantly increase the risk for development of hypokalemia [8].

MI patients were found to have hyponatremia which could be attributed to the fact that non osmotic secretion of vasopressin impairs the water secretion causing dilutional hyponatremia [9]. AVP or vasopressin is known to regulate tone and cardiac contraction and may adversely affect cardiac hemodynamics and myocardial remodelling. Hyponatremia on admission or early development of hyponatremia in patients with acute STElevation myocardial infarction is an independent predictor of 30-day mortality, and prognosis worsens with the severity of hyponatremia [10].

CONCLUSION:

It is concluded that reduction in sodium level was assessed only in patients with AMI as compared to healthy persons. Estimation of serum electrolyte is of utmost importance for diagnosis and prognosis of AMI.

REFERENCES:

1. Bertel O, Buhler FR, Baitsch G, Ritz R: Plasma adrenaline and noradrenaline in patients with acute myocardial infarctionrelationship to ventricular arrhythmias of varying severity. *Chest* 82, 64 (1982)
2. Goldstein DS: Plasma norepinephrine as an indicator of sympathetic neural activity in clinical cardiology. *Am J Cardiol*48, 1147 (1981)
3. Myoishi M, Kitakaze M. A role of magnesium: magnesium in the therapy for cardiovascular diseases. *Clin Calcium*. 2005;15(2):265-70.
4. Alizadehasl A, Sepasi F, Azarfarin R, Ghaffari S. Hypokalemia, arrhythmias and early outcomes in acute myocardial infarction. *Res J Bio Sci*. 2008;3(9):1130-2.
5. Solomon RJ, Cole AG. Importance of potassium in patients with acute myocardial infarction. *Acta Med Scand*. 1981 Jan 12;209(S647):87-93.
6. Beck OA, Hochrein H: Serumkaliumspiegel und Herzrhythmusstörung bei akutem Myocardinfarkt. *Z Kardiol*66, 187 (1977)
7. Dyckner T, Helmers C, Lundman T, Wester PO: Initial serum potassium level in relation to early complications and prognosis in patients with acute myocardial infarction. *Acta Med Scand* 197, 207 (1975)
8. Morgan DB: Hypokalaemia and diuretics. *Roy Soc Med Intern Congr Symp Series* 44, 3 (1981)
9. Nordrehaug JE, von der Lippe G: Hypokalaemia and ventricular fibrillation in acute myocardial infarction. *Br Heart J* 50, 525 (1983)
10. Nordrehaug JE, von der Lippe G: Serum potassium concentrations are inversely related to ventricular, but not to atrial, arrhythmias in acute myocardial infarction. *Eur Heart J* 7, 224 (1986).